

Institute Project Assignment Report

A pilot project to explore the feasibility of dating rock surfaces and carbonate deposits using luminescence dating

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1. Project description

The Desert Research Institute Luminescence Dating Laboratory (DRILL) aims to develop new methods in luminescence dating that are specifically calibrated to Nevada's geology and archaeology, and to expand the range of sample types that can be dated in Nevada and elsewhere. This pilot project focuses on expanding DRILL's capacity to dating rock surfaces and carbonate deposits such as travertine and tufa.

Luminescence dating determines when a mineral (typically quartz or feldspar) was last exposed to sunlight, and uses the optical properties of these minerals to determine the burial age of sediments, rocks, or artifacts (see review in Roberts and Lian, 2015). It is particularly crucial for sites that lack organic material suitable for radiocarbon dating, or sites that date to beyond the upper threshold of radiocarbon dating (~55,000 years). Luminescence dating techniques are most commonly applied to silt or sand samples that help determine the timing of landform creation, climate change or even past human occupation. But in recent years, significant advances have been made in dating rock surfaces (Habermann et al. 2000; Greilich et al., 2005; Vafiadou et al., 2007; Simms et al., 2011; Sohbati, 2015; Chapot et al., 2012; Freiesleben et al., 2015; Simkins et al., 2016; Khasawneh et al., 2019) as well as quartz grains encased in carbonate deposits and limestone (Rich et al., 2003; Prescott and Habermehl, 2008; Liritzis et al., 2008; 2010).

Luminescence ages from rocks are important for sites that lack adequate sand/silt for traditional luminescence dating techniques, as well as sites that are contaminated by mobile fine grain materials that severely post-date (underestimate) the true age of the landform or artifact. Applications of rock surface dating include refining the chronology of sea level change (Simms et al., 2011), the advance and retreat of glaciers (Jenkins et al., 2018), and the construction of monuments, buildings or walls by ancient humans (Liritzis, 2010), to name a few. Luminescence ages of sand grains encased in carbonate deposits such as tufa (Rich et al., 2003; Prescott and Habermehl, 2008) can also help determine the timing of past wet and dry climatic periods linked to the expansion and contraction of pluvial lakes or the (de-)activation of springs.

The development of luminescence dating techniques for rocks must include two steps: 1) the identification of suitable luminescence signals for dating, and 2) the development of suitable methods and models for quantifying the dose rate of rocks as well as their burial environment. The main goal of this pilot project focuses on Step 1, the identification of suitable luminescence signals for dating. Information gleaned from this work will help us focus future research efforts (Step 2) on rock types that show the most promise for rock surface dating.

2. Background – Luminescence dating

Luminescence dating refers to a myriad of techniques that are used to determine that last time minerals (typically quartz or potassium-rich (K) feldspar) were exposed to sunlight or heat (Aitken, 1998). In the case of sunlight, luminescence ages tell us how long a deposit or artifact has been buried. After quartz and feldspar minerals are buried, they are exposed to ionizing radiation emitted from the surrounding sediments and cosmic rays from outer space that penetrate the ground surface. At the molecular scale, this radiation re-mobilizes electrons, which in turn accumulate within defects (so-called "traps") inside the crystal lattice. These defects exist in the form of structural imperfections or impurities. The longer a mineral is buried, the more electrons accumulate within the traps.

To calculate an age, we need to define: 1) the amount of radiation absorbed by the mineral during burial (also called the paleodose and estimated in the lab by measurement of the equivalent dose, or D_e), and 2) the rate at which the mineral was irradiated during burial (called the environmental dose rate or D_a). We then calculate the age (in ka) as the D_e value (in Gy) divided by D_a (in Gy/ka).

To estimate the paleodose, the mineral is stimulated with a light source in the lab (blue or green light in the case of quartz), which evicts the electrons from their traps and results in the emission of photons of light (luminescence). The luminescence intensity (total photon counts) is measured by a photomultiplier tube and provides an estimate of the amount of radiation absorbed by the mineral during burial. To measure the environmental dose rate, the quantity of radionuclides in the surrounding sediments are either measured directly or are estimated using radiation detectors in the field or in the lab.

2.1 Tasks and Objectives

To achieve the goal of this project, I tested previously published rock cutting and mineral extraction techniques on a range of rock types from Nevada and determined which rock types yield luminescence signals that appear most promising for luminescence dating. The research objectives have been achieved through the following tasks:

- 1) Collecting a series of rock types from a range of geological terrains in Nevada (Crafford, 2007).
- 2) Testing previously published sediment extraction procedures for limestone surfaces (Liritz et al., 2008; 2010) and carbonate deposits (Rich et al., 2003; Prescott and Habermehl, 2008) at DRILL.
- 3) Testing previously published drilling and cutting procedures for volcanic, plutonic and sedimentary rock surfaces at the Department of Anthropology, University of Washington (UW), Seattle, where drilling and cutting equipment for rock surface dating is housed. This work was done with the assistance of the UW Luminescence Lab Director and Associate Professor, James Feathers, who has expertise in rock surface dating (Feathers et al., 2019).
- 4) Conducting luminescence measurements of all extracted minerals from all rock types at DRILL to characterize their luminescence signals, and to assess their suitability for dating.

3. Sample collection and processing

3.1 Rock and tufa samples

Rock samples of a range of lithologies have been collected from various locations and geological terrains in Nevada (Table 1, Figs 1, 2). Past research around the world has shown that some rock lithologies are more suited to rock surface dating using luminescence methods than others. The most promising results have been obtained using luminescence signals from quartz and feldspar from relatively homogeneous surfaces of sandstone, quartzite and granites (Meyer et al., 2018, and references therein). Some success has also been achieved using volcanic rocks (Feathers et al., 2019), however basaltic rocks have proven to be problematic (Tsukamoto and Duller, 2008; Tsukamoto et al., 2011). In this study, a range of rock types was sampled for testing that included felsic volcanic and plutonic rocks, basalt, metasedimentary silt and sandstones, as well as vein quartz and siliceous sinter.

Limestone and calcium carbonate has yet to yield luminescence signals desirable for luminescence dating (Galloway, 2002), however, success has been achieved in dating quartz grains extracted from limestone as well as other carbonate deposits using acid treatments (e.g., Rich et al., 2003; Prescott and Habermehl, 2008). Therefore, in this study, limestone collected from Coal Valley, Lincoln County (Table 1, Fig. 2B) was used to determine the feasibility of extracting quartz or feldspar grains from its surface (e.g., Liritzis et al., 2010). Tufa was also collected from ancient pluvial lake deposits in Jessup embayment, Churchill County (Adams and Wesnousky, 1998; 1999) to assess the feasibility of extracting detrital quartz and feldspar for dating (Table 1, Figs 2C, 3). Two pieces of lithoid tufa (R5 and R6) were collected from an ancient cobble beach terrace thought to be associated with the ~140-280 ka Eetza pluvial lake highstand (Adams pers. comm.). A third piece of thicker more porous tufa (R7) was collected from boulder deposits on the opposite side of the valley ~1500 ft north (Figs 2C, 3). Both tufas were

extracted from the surfaces volcanic cobbles or boulders and appear to be the genetic equivalent of “beachrock” following the classification scheme of Benson (1994). Because this study is focused solely on the luminescence signal properties of the samples, and not sample dose rates or ages, rock samples were collected from the ground surface and no attempts were made to prevent their exposure to light prior to testing.

Table 1. Rock sample locations, lithologies and processing. See Figs 1 and 2 for sample locations.

Rock sampling area		Rock samples ¹	Geological terrain (from Crafford, 2007)	Location (lat/long in decimal degrees)	Laboratory tests
1	Keystone Canyon	Siltstone (R1, R2, R3) Mudstone (R4)	Jurassic/Triassic metavolcanic rocks and Pliocene/Miocene tuffaceous rocks and andesites.	39.5524, -119.8496	Cored and sliced for signal measurements.
2	Bowers Mansion	3 granite boulders (R1, R2, R3)	Miocene to Jurassic felsic phaneritic intrusive rocks.	39.2870, -119.8388	Cored and sliced for signal measurements.
3	Jessup embayment	3 pieces of tufa (R5, R6, R7) 1 basalt rock (R1)	Oligocene and Miocene andesite and basalt flows overlain by Quaternary lacustrine deposits. R5 and R6 are sampled from what is thought to be the Eetza pluvial highstand. R7 is sampled from a slightly lower elevation, near the base of basalt cliffs to the north.	39.9425, -118.8410	Polyminerals and KF extracted from tufa for signal measurements. Basalt cored and sliced for signal measurements.
4	Coal Valley (NE bar)	1 limestone pebble (R1)	Palaeozoic siltstone, limestone, dolomite, shale and sandstone, and Eocene to Miocene intermediate rhyolitic flows and siliceous tuff. Bedrock is overlain by Quaternary lacustrine and alluvial deposits.	37.9305, -115.2726	Rock surface sampled for sediment (filing + HCl treatment).
5	Coal Valley (SW side of basin)	1 limestone rock (R3) 1 silt/sandstone (R1) 1 silt/sandstone (R2)		37.8737, -115.3695	Limestone rock surface sampled for sediment (filing + HCl treatment). Non-limestone rocks cored and sliced for signal measurements.
6	Coal Valley (West Golden Gate Range)	3 limestone rocks (R3, R4, R8)		37.9356, -115.3668	Rock surfaces sampled for sediment (filing + HCl treatment).
7	Coal Valley (Drainage Floor NW)	3 limestone rocks (R8, R11, R12) 1 andesite (R2) 1 rhyolite (R5) 1 siltstone (R7) 1 andesite (R14)		38.0400, -115.3511	Limestone rock surfaces sampled for sediment (filing + HCl treatment). Non-limestone rocks cored and sliced for signal measurements.
8	Prison Hill, Carson City	1 piece of vein quartz	Jurassic to Miocene undivided nonporphyritic quartz monzonite overlain by Quaternary alluvial fan and floodplain deposits.	39.1054, -119.7316	Milled for signal testing.
9	Steamboat Springs	1 piece of sinter	Pliocene to Holocene siliceous sinter deposits and basalts overlying Mesozoic to Miocene intrusive plutonic and volcanogenic, carbonate and clastic rocks.	39.3678, -119.7758	Milled for signal testing.

¹ The sedimentary rock samples (mudstones, siltstones and sandstones) may have a volcanogenic origin.

Figure 1. Map of all rock sample locations. Refer to Table 1 for sample area numbers.

Figure 2. A) Sampling areas Keystone Canyon (1), Steamboat Springs (9), Bowers Mansion (2) and Prison Hill (8). B) Sampling areas in Coal Valley, Lincoln County (4-7). C) The Jessup embayment preserving a former pluvial lake highstand (lithoid terrace, 3) (Adams & Wesnousky, 1998; 1999). See Table 1 for rock sample details.

Figure 3. Tufa collected from Jessup embayment. 'A' and 'B' show dense lithoid tufa collected from an ancient cobble beach terrace associated with the Eetza pluvial lake highstand (R5, R6). 'C' and 'D' show the thicker more porous tufa (R7) collected from a boulder deposit on the opposite side of the valley at a slightly lower elevation.

3.2 Sample processing

3.2.1 Sedimentary, volcanic and plutonic rocks

Sedimentary, volcanic and plutonic rock samples were cored and sliced at the Department of Anthropology, University of Washington before signal testing at the luminescence dating lab at DRI (DRILL). The surfaces of rock samples were cored using a drill press and a water-cooled diamond drill bit with a ~10 mm internal diameter. All coring was conducted in dark-lab conditions dimly illuminated with safe red-filtered light to prevent white light exposure of the rock cores. Cores from all rock lithologies rarely cracked and generally stayed intact.

Cores were sliced (also in safe-light conditions) into ~1 mm thick slices using a water-cooled 0.4 mm thick diamond wafer-blade mounted on a Buehler low-speed saw. Slices cut from granite samples (Bowers Mansion Granite) tended to crumble, whereas slices cut from fine grain volcanic or sedimentary rock were more likely to stay intact. All rock slices were hand ground using a mortar and pestle into a fine powder prior to signal measurement. Signals from intact rock slices were not measured because this requires calibration of the reader using artificially dosed calibration quartz slices, which have yet to be developed (DTU Nutech Product Catalogue, www.nutech.dtu.dk).

3.2.2 Limestone

Limestone rock surfaces were filed using a metal file to a depth of 1-3 mm, and the filings were diluted in weak (10%) HCl acid overnight to dissolve CaCO₃ following the methods of Liritzis et al. (2010). Any remaining clastic sediments were rinsed, weighed and dried. The filings from one limestone sample (Coal Valley NE bar) yielded no sediment, while the filings from all other samples yielded anywhere from ~1% to ~32% sediment, the highest concentrations occurring in rocks from the NW side of Coal Valley (Table 2, Fig. 2B).

3.2.3 Tufa

Tufa samples were dissolved in 36% HCl, then treated with 30% H₂O₂ to remove any organic components prior to rinsing, weighing and drying. Samples R5 and R7 yielded ~5% of sediment and sample R6, collected within a few meters of R5, yielded ~13% sediment (Table 2). The 90-180 μm fraction of R5, and the 180-250 μm of R7 were further density separated into quartz (2.62 g/cm³ < ρ < 2.68 g/cm³) and K-feldspar (ρ < 2.58 g/cm³) fractions using lithium heteropolytungstate (LST). The 90-180 μm fraction from R5 was comprised of 5% quartz and 58% K-feldspar. The 180-250 μm fraction from R7 consisted of 5% quartz and 80% K-feldspar. While the quantity of quartz is sparse in these samples, the quantity of K-feldspar was adequate for signal testing and D_e measurement (Table 2).

3.2.4 Dosimetry

Dose rates were estimated from three different rock types analyzed in this study including two sedimentary rocks, one plutonic rock and two pieces of lithoid tufa (Table 3). These samples were milled into a fine powder and sent to ALS Minerals, Reno, NV for U, Th, Rb and K content analyses. Th and Rb samples were fused with lithium borate and measured with ICP-MS. K₂O was measured on bulk sample with ICP-AES and converted to % K. Dose rates (Gy/ka) were calculated using the conversion factors of Liritzis et al. (2013) assuming negligible water content within the rocks, and 1 ± 2% water content within the tufa. All rock and tufa samples in this study were collected from the ground surface, and dose rate contributions from surrounding sediments were not estimated. However, age estimates from ancient rocks or tufa should include any dose rate contribution from surrounding sediments, and these can be modelled using geochemistry analysis of separate bag samples (e.g., Simms et al., 2011).

Table 2. Quantities of sediment extracted from limestone samples collected from Coal Valley and tufa samples collected from Jessup embayment.

Limestone samples (organized by sampling area in Coal Valley)	Initial rock mass (g)	Mass of filings (g)	Mass of filings post-HCl treatment ¹	Estimated number of aliquots	Extracted sediment (%)	
1. NE bar	R1	52	0.153	0	0	
5. SW side of basin	R3	360	0.523	0.025	5-10	4.8
6. West Golden Gate Range	R3	454	0.633	0.047	10-20	7.4
	R4	129	0.395	0.014	<5	3.5
	R6	30	0.209	0.002	<5	1.0
	R8	41	0.320	0.009	<5	2.8
	R9	33	0.396	0.005	<5	1.3
7. Drainage Fl NW	R8	167	0.744	0.054	10-20	7.3
	R11	233	1.257	0.404	≥50	32.1
	R12	503	0.738	0.174	≥50	23.6
Tufa samples (Jessup embayment)	Initial tufa mass (g)	Mass of extracted sediment (g)	Extracted sediment (%)	Estimated number of aliquots	Extracted Q and KF from sand fraction (g)	
	R5	239	12.4	5.2	>50	0.044 (Q), 0.752 (KF) ²
	R6	230	30.3	13.2	>50	N/A
	R7	1814	91.7	5.1	>100	0.451 (Q), 4.860 (KF) ²

¹ Sample was treated with 5% HCl overnight, or until no further reaction occurred.

² Quartz (Q) and potassium-rich feldspar (KF) was extracted through density liquid separation from the 90-180 μm grain size fraction, only.

³ Quartz (Q) and potassium-rich feldspar (KF) was extracted through density liquid separation from the 180-250 μm grain size fraction, only.

Table 3. Radionuclide concentrations and dose rates for select samples from Jessup embayment, Keystone Canyon and Bowers Mansion.

Rock sample	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	K (%)	Rb (ppm)	Alpha dose rate (Gy/ka)	Beta dose rate (Gy/ka)	Gamma dose rate (Gy/ka)	Internal beta dose rate ¹ (Gy/ka)	Cosmic dose rate (Gy/ka)	Total dose rate ² (Gy/ka)
Jessup embayment										
Tufa (R5)	1.01 ± 0.10	0.76 ± 0.08	0.13 ± 0.01	6.40 ± 0.64	0.024 ± 0.009	0.240 ± 0.017	0.177 ± 0.013	0.488 ± 0.162	0.294 ± 0.029	1.23 ± 0.17
Tufa (R6)	1.20 ± 0.120	0.88 ± 0.09	0.14 ± 0.01	6.80 ± 0.68	0.028 ± 0.011	0.279 ± 0.020	0.207 ± 0.015	0.488 ± 0.162	0.294 ± 0.029	1.30 ± 0.17
Keystone Canyon										
Siltstone (R2)	2.28 ± 0.23	8.21 ± 0.82	2.66 ± 0.27	87.8 ± 8.78	0.450 ± 0.221	2.661 ± 0.006	1.303 ± 0.082	0.122 ± 0.095	0.304 ± 0.030	4.84 ± 0.26
Mudstone (R4)	2.50 ± 0.25	7.52 ± 0.75	2.25 ± 0.22	64.6 ± 0.65	0.428 ± 0.206	2.336 ± 0.004	1.192 ± 0.073	0.128 ± 0.091	0.304 ± 0.030	4.38 ± 0.24
Bowers Mansion										
Granite (R3)	3.13 ± 0.31	10.25 ± 1.03	2.23 ± 0.22	86.0 ± 8.6	0.072 ± 0.023	2.239 ± 0.002	1.388 ± 0.082	0.848 ± 0.248	0.307 ± 0.031	4.85 ± 0.26

¹ Internal beta dose rates were calculated assuming 10 ± 2% K inside feldspar grains used for D_e measurement following Smedley et al. (2012).

² For tufa samples, total dose rates were calculated using the grain size of the sand fraction used for D_e measurement (90-180 μm). Total dose rates of the rock samples were calculated assuming a grain size of 4-63 μm for siltstone, 1-63 μm for mudstone and 180-300 μm for granite.

4. Luminescence signal measurement

Due to the small quantities of material available for signal measurement from the rock slices and limestone surfaces, I focused on the signal properties from unseparated (polyminerall) samples to see if signals suitable for dating could be measured without further mineral separation. Because tufa samples yielded more sediment for experimentation, measurements were made on multi-grain aliquots of both polyminerall and density-separated K-feldspar (KF) fractions, as well as on single grains of KF. The difference between multi-grain and single-grain luminescence dating techniques, as well as the signal characteristics of quartz and feldspar are explained in more detail below.

4.1 Multi-grain aliquots vs single grains

Luminescence dating techniques were first developed to measure D_e values from multi-grain aliquots of sample where the total number of grains per aliquot depended largely on aliquot and grain size (e.g., Arnold and Roberts, 2009, table 5). The sample D_e value used to calculate an age in this case was calculated as the average or weighted mean D_e from ~5-50 multi-grain aliquots, where the signal from one aliquot contained multiple signals from multiple individual grains. There are two problems with this method: i) grains with signals that are unsuitable for dating still contribute to the luminescence signal of a multi-grain aliquot, and ii) it's difficult to identify and reject incompletely bleached grains in a sample because their signals will be combined with all other grains in an aliquot. In the late 1990's and early 2000's, tools and techniques were developed for the measurement of individual sand-sized grains (e.g., Roberts et al., 1998; 1999), and these included laser stimulation sources in place of LEDs (Bøtter-Jensen et al., 2000). This allows us to examine large ($n=100$ or more) distributions of D_e values from a sample and perform more sophisticated statistical analyses to identify the D_e values that represent the burial event of interest. For example, single-grain distributions can expose incompletely bleached grains in water lain sediments (Arnold et al., 2007), or grains derived from two different sedimentary layers that have been mixed together (Roberts et al., 2000; Arnold and Roberts, 2009).

In this study multi-grain aliquots of all polyminerall and KF fractions were mounted onto 10 mm diameter stainless steel discs using silicon oil as an adhesive. Aliquot diameters were ~4 mm and their luminescence signals and D_e measurements were measured in one of two Risø TL/OSL-DA-20 readers equipped with a $^{90}\text{Sr}/^{90}\text{Y}$ beta radiation source. Single grains of KF were mounted onto single-grain discs, each containing 100 300 μm diameter holes. Single grains were measured in the same Risø readers using IR lasers. The luminescence signals from quartz and KF that are routinely used for dating have different emissions: quartz emits UV light, while KF emits violet light. Thus, each mineral required its own stimulation source and optical filters for signal detection.

4.2 Quartz

The luminescence signal from quartz consists of a UV peak emission at ~365 nm when the sample is stimulated with blue light. Blue light is used as a stimulation source because it is sufficiently high energy to eject electrons from the source traps of interest, but low enough not to overlap with the luminescence signal (Fig. 4). For multigrain aliquots of quartz, blue light stimulation was made with a cluster of blue LEDs (NICHIA type NSPB-500AS) with a peak emission at 470 nm and a total power of 80 mW/cm². Luminescence signals were detected with a bialkali EMI 9235Q photomultiplier tube (PMT) fitted with Hoya U-340 filters that transmit UV light.

A

B

Figure 4. A) Quartz luminescence emission spectra (from Huntley et al. 1991). B) Emission spectra of blue LEDs used to stimulate quartz, and the transmission range of the U-340 filters (from the Guide to the Riso TL/OSL Reader, DTU Nutech, June 2017).

Luminescence signals are routinely measured in “continuous-wave” (CW) mode, where the light source is held at a constant power during stimulation. This results in a so-called “decay curve” where the maximum photon count rate is observed at the start of stimulation before declining with stimulation time (columns 2 and 3 of Table 4, Fig. 5). The first 1 to 2 s of the quartz optical decay curve is most useful for dating because it is the result of electrons being evicted from a specific set of traps that form the “fast component”. The fast component of the signal is ideal because it is depleted at the fastest rate during sun exposure (ensuring adequate bleaching of grains during the most recent burial event), and it is stable (i.e., it does not fade) for geological time periods of hundreds of thousands of years. The latter parts of the decay curve consist of higher proportions of medium and slow components. These components are less ideal for dating because they take longer to deplete during sun exposure

(resulting in high residual signals that lead to age over-estimates), they can suffer more from thermal transfer effects, and some of them are not thermally stable over geological timescales.

Standard D_e measurement from quartz extracts typically involves light stimulation at 125°C to rid of a thermally unstable charge contribution to the signal. If contamination from feldspar is anticipated, blue light stimulation is often preceded by stimulation with infrared (IR) diodes (see Section 4.3) to bleach any signal contribution from feldspar without further bleaching the OSL signal from quartz (also known as a post-IR OSL measurement, Roberts, 2007). For sediment extracts from all samples in this study, both the OSL (here meaning blue light stimulation) and the post-IR OSL were measured to determine: a) if there is a signal from quartz, and b) does this signal have a contribution from contaminating feldspar (column 2, Tables 4 and 5). Samples with signals coming mainly from quartz will have OSL and the post-IR OSL signals of similar intensity implying negligible signal reduction due to IR bleaching of feldspar. Samples with signals coming mainly, or in part, from contaminating feldspar will have post-IR OSL signals that are less intense than the OSL signals, as well as a prominent IR signal.

Table 4 shows luminescence signals measured from rock slices and sediment from tufa. Only three rocks with quartz with bright signals (i.e., >500 photon counts/s) show little or negligible reduction after the IR bleach (column 2). These include two siltstones from Keystone Canyon (R1 and R3) and one silt/sandstone from the SW side of Coal Valley (R2). Samples with dim (i.e., <500 photon counts/s) or negligible OSL signals include basalt from Jessup embayment (R1), one silt/sandstone from SW Coal Valley (R1), vein quartz from Prison Hill and siliceous sinter from Steamboat Springs (column 2, Table 4).

All sediments extracted from limestone surfaces with bright OSL signals show appreciable decrease in intensity after IR stimulation suggesting that feldspar is present (column 2, Table 5). Three limestone rocks show OSL and IRSL signals that are dim or <500 counts/s (R3 from SW Coal Valley, and R11 and R12 from NW Coal Valley) suggesting that these samples cannot be dated with any precision.

Fast, medium and slow components of the quartz luminescence signal can be best viewed by measuring the sample using “linear modulation” or LM-OSL (Fig. 5 inset). This method measures the luminescence signal using a light source that is increasing in power over time (Bulur, 1996). This yields a signal comprised of a series of peaks, the first of which (and hopefully brightest) is the fast component. When this initial peak is small or missing, we can infer that the sample has a weak or missing fast component that is required for dating.

LM-OSL curves were measured from all limestone sediment extracts (column 4 of Table 5) and rock slices with post-IR OSL signals that rapidly decayed in the first second of stimulation, suggesting the presence of a fast component (column 4, Table 4). Only two rocks, siltstones R1 and R3 from Keystone Canyon, show evidence of a fast component from quartz (Table 4). None of the limestone samples yielded fast components that are prominent enough for dating (Table 5). The most prominent fast component peak from limestone is present in the LM-OSL curve of R4 from Coal Valley, West Golden Gate Range. However, because this peak and the post-IR OSL signal are both drastically dwarfed by the IRSL signal from feldspar (see below), future tests should focus on the suitability of feldspar, rather than quartz, for dating this sample.

Figure 5. Natural CW-OSL signals from quartz and K-feldspar from Calvert Island, central coast of British Columbia, Canada. Typical LM-OSL signals from quartz from Calvert Island (CIBS3) and from the Peace River region, interior BC (sample BRD2) are shown in the inset graph. Note that Calvert Island quartz lacks a datable fast component, which explains the low-intensity CW-OSL signal. Data are from Neudorf et al. (2015).

4.3 K-feldspar

KF is traditionally stimulated using infrared (IR) light at 50°C and has a peak luminescence emission at ~410 nm that is transmitted through Corning 7-59 and Schott BG39 filters (Fig. 6). This emission is also referred to as the IR stimulated luminescence or IRSL₅₀ signal. Feldspar IRSL₅₀ signals are commonly much brighter than quartz OSL signals, especially in samples from near mountain ranges where quartz signals often have poor sensitivity (e.g., Bacon et al., 2018). Therefore, in polymineral mixtures this measurement configuration is also commonly used to detect feldspar signals, with the assumption that the quartz signal is too dim to significantly contaminate the signal from feldspar (e.g., Frouin et al., 2017).

For multi-grain aliquots of polymineral sediment or KF extracts measured in this study, IR stimulation was made with a cluster of Vishay TSFF 5210 IR diodes with peak emission at 870 nm, and maximum power of 145 mW/cm² at the sample position. The same IR diodes were also used to detect the signals of contaminating feldspar grains in density-separated quartz samples; as part of these IR emissions will transmit through U-340 filters (see Section 4.2 above). Single-grain measurements were made with an IR laser emitting at 830 nm at a maximum power of 150 mW/cm². Corning 7-59 and Schott BG39 filters were used for K-feldspar signal detection for the purposes of signal testing and D_e measurement.

A

B

Figure 6. A) K-feldspar luminescence emission spectra (from Huntley et al., 1991). B) The emission spectra of IR diodes and the transmission spectra of the Corning 7-59 and Schott BG39 filters, also known as the Blue Filter Pack (from the Guide to the Riso TL/OSL Reader, DTU Nutech, June 2017).

Tables 4 and 5 (column 3) show the IRSL signals measured at 50°C from rock slices, tufa and limestone sediment extracts. IRSL signals were not measured from the vein quartz or siliceous sinter. Most rock samples measured (9 out of 13) exhibit an initial IRSL signal of 1000 counts/s or more in intensity, with four samples (Keystone Canyon siltstone (R1), Jessup embayment basalt (R1), SW Coal Valley silt/sandstones (R1 and R2)) showing signals that are too dim to be dated (<500 counts/s). Five out of seven limestone samples yielded IRSL signals sufficiently bright for dating (>500 counts/s), and one of the dimmer samples (R3 of SW Coal Valley) shows an initial count rate of ~325 counts/s that may still yield adequate age estimates albeit with a lower precision. The only limestone sample yielding a signal that is clearly too dim for dating comes from NW Coal Valley (R11).

Table 4. OSL, IRSL, post-IR OSL and LM-OSL signals for rock and tufa samples collected in this study, grouped by sampling area (Table 1). The UV filter is used to detect 365 nm wavelength luminescence emissions from quartz (or contaminating feldspar using IR stimulation), while the violet filter detects 410 nm wavelength emissions from feldspar.

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
1. Keystone Canyon			
Siltstone (R1) 			
Siltstone (R2) 			

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
<p>Siltstone (R3)</p>	<p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>— OSL — IRSL - - post-IR OSL</p>	<p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>— IRSL</p>	<p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>— LM-OSL</p>
<p>Mudstone (R4)</p>	<p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>— OSL — IRSL - - post-IR OSL</p>	<p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>— IRSL</p>	

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
2. Bowers Mansion			
Granite (R3) 			
3. Jessup embayment			
Polymineral sediment from tufa (R5) 			

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
<p>Basalt (R1)</p>			
5. Coal Valley (SW side of basin)			
<p>Silt/sandstone (R1)</p>			

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
<p>Silt/sandstone (R2)</p>			
7. Coal Valley (Drainage Floor NW)			
<p>Andesite (R2)</p>			

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
Rhyolite (R5) 			
Siltstone (R7) 			
Andesite (R14) 			

Rock samples (Drill holes are 10 mm in diameter)	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
8. Prison Hill, Carson City			
Vein quartz (scale is metric) <p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>OSL</p>			
9. Steamboat Springs			
Sinter (scale is metric) <p>Photon counts / s</p> <p>Stimulation time (s)</p> <p>LM-OSL</p>			

Table 5. OSL, IRSL, post-IR OSL and LM-OSL signals for limestone sediment extracts, grouped by sampling area (Table 1). The UV filter is used to detect 365 nm wavelength luminescence emissions from quartz (or contaminating feldspar using IR stimulation), while the violet filter detects 410 nm wavelength emissions from feldspar.

Rock samples	UV filter (U-340)	Violet filter (Schott BG-3 & BG39)	UV filter (U-340)
5. Coal Valley (SW side of basin)			
Limestone (R3) 			
6. Coal Valley (West Golden Gate Range)			
Limestone (R3) 			

Past research suggests that, unlike quartz, feldspar luminescence signals are not comprised of discrete components generated from unique trap types, but rather a single trap type that exhibits a range of signal stabilities and bleaching rates depending on how it is measured (Thomsen et al., 2008; Buylaert et al., 2009; Jain and Ankaergaard, 2011). The main signal characteristic of feldspars that determines their suitability for dating is the fading rate, and this is discussed in more detail below.

4.4 Anomalous fading in feldspar

It has long been known that the luminescence signal from feldspar suffers from anomalous (or athermal) fading, where the signal will fade with time, even in the absence of light or heat (Wintle, 1973; Huntley and Lian, 2006). This is typically attributed to quantum mechanical tunneling of electrons from their traps to nearby defects (Visocekas, 1985). The fading rate of a sample can be measured in the laboratory and corrected for if it is not too high, and if the sample is not too old (i.e., ~20 ka or less) (Huntley and Lamothe, 2001). In these cases, the correction model of Huntley and Lamothe (2001) is typically applied. Some correction methods have been developed for older samples (>100 ka) (Lamothe et al., 2003; Kars and Wallinga, 2009), but these tend to introduce large uncertainties in age calculations.

Researchers searching for a non-fading component in the feldspar signal have discovered that IR signals that are measured at higher stimulation temperatures (i.e., 180, 225 or 290°C) after an IR bleach at 50°C, either fade less, or not at all (Thomsen et al., 2008; Reimann et al., 2011; Thiel et al., 2011). This has led to the development of a suite of measurement protocols targeting a “post-infrared infrared” or post-IRIR signal that are now widely used (e.g., Újvári et al., 2014; E et al., 2018; Buckland et al., 2019; Davis et al., 2019; Bacon et al., 2020). A disadvantage of post-IRIR signals is that they often have slower bleaching rates during sun exposure than the traditional IRSL₅₀ signal, and modern samples may carry a significant residual signal that must be corrected for (e.g., Reimann et al., 2011; Li et al., 2014; Neudorf et al., 2014).

A variant of the post-IRIR signal is termed the multi-elevated temperature (MET) IRSL signal (Li and Li, 2011). This method measures the IRSL signal at successively higher stimulation temperatures after the initial 50°C stimulation to generate a D_e vs stimulation temperature plot. A plateau in such a plot can be used to infer whether a sample has been fully bleached prior to burial, and also indicates the region where the D_e is not affected by fading (e.g., Clarkson et al., 2020). This measurement procedure is thought to be more efficient at removing the fading-prone charge at lower stimulation temperatures than the original post-IRIR protocols, and has been shown to be superior to post-IRIR methods in old samples with natural doses exceeding ~425 Gy (Li and Li, 2012). As with the post-IRIR methods, the MET-IRSL method suffers from slower bleaching rates and residual doses that may require correction in some samples (Li et al., 2013b; Rui et al., 2020a).

In this study, I test the suitability of three IRSL signals on the rock samples: i) the traditional IRSL signal measured at 50°C (also known as the IRSL₅₀ signal), ii) the post-IRIR signal using an elevated stimulation temperature of 290°C (i.e., the pIRIR₂₉₀ signal) and iii) the MET-IRSL signal.

5. The Single Aliquot Regenerative Dose Protocol

The single aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) protocol (Wallinga et al., 2000; Wintle and Murray, 2006) is the most common method of determining D_e from a sample. This method consists of two steps: i) measuring the natural luminescence signal, and ii) measuring the sample’s luminescence response to a series of known, successively increasing laboratory given doses. The second step is required to build a so-called “dose response curve” onto which the natural signal is plotted to quantify the D_e value (Fig. 7). All natural (L_n) and regenerative dose (L_x) signal measurements are followed by a test dose measurement (termed T_n after the measurement of L_n

and T_x after measurement of L_x), where the signal is measured after a small laboratory-given dose that is kept consistent throughout the protocol. L_n and L_x are divided by T_n and T_x , respectively to correct for any sensitivity changes in the signal that might occur during SAR due to sample irradiation, heating and stimulation. The first SAR cycle measures L_n/T_n , and all subsequent SAR cycles (typically 4-6) measure L_x/T_x to establish the DRC (Table 6). All SAR cycles are performed on one individual aliquot of sample to determine a D_e value, and typically multiple aliquots (5-50 for multi-grain aliquot analyses, or >100 for single-grain analyses) are measured to determine a distribution of D_e values for the sample to determine an age.

In addition to the regenerative dose points measured to establish the DRC, two additional regenerative dose points are measured for quality control purposes. These include the repeat-dose point (i.e., one regenerative dose point is measured twice), and a zero-dose point (i.e. L_x/T_x is measured after no dose is given). The repeat dose point is used to calculate a “recycling ratio”, which is the ratio between the two repeat regenerative dose points. If this ratio is within 10% of unity, we can be assured that the test dose has adequately corrected for sensitivity changes during SAR. The zero-dose point is used to calculate “recuperation”, which is a combination of charge that has not been sufficiently depleted at the end of each SAR cycle, as well as excess accumulated charge as a result of thermal transfer during the preheat. Samples that behave well should have recuperated signals that are ~5% or less of the natural signal.

Figure 7. A dose response curve measured from Tasmanian quartz (Neudorf et al., 2019). " L_n/T_n " is the sensitivity-corrected natural signal, " L_x/T_x " is the sensitivity-corrected regenerative dose signal, and D_0 is the saturation dose of this sample. See text for explanation.

Table 6. The single aliquot regenerative (SAR) dose protocol.

Steps in a SAR cycle	Purpose
1. Natural / Regenerative Dose	In SAR cycle 1, no action is taken as the sample contains the natural dose to be measured. In subsequent SAR cycles, a regenerative dose is administered to the sample to construct a dose response curve.
2. Preheat	The sample is heated to rid of thermally unstable charge.
3. Stimulation (IRSL/BOSL) ¹ → Ln, Lx	The sample is stimulated with a light source to detect luminescence emissions associated with the natural/regenerative dose. IR light is typically used to detect feldspar luminescence, while blue light (BOSL) is typically used to detect quartz luminescence.
4. Test dose	A small radiation dose is administered to the sample that is the same in every SAR cycle.
5. Preheat	The sample is heated to rid of thermally unstable charge.
6. Stimulation (IRSL/BOSL) ¹ → Tn, Tx	The sample is stimulated with a light source to detect luminescence emissions associated with the test dose. The test dose signal is used to correct the natural/regenerative dose signals for sensitivity changes.
7. Hotwash (IRSL/BOSL)	The sample is stimulated with a light source at high temperature to rid of recuperated charge, or charge that was insufficiently depleted during Step 6.
8. Return to step 1.	

¹Ln = natural signal, Lx = regenerative dose signal. Tn = test dose signal measured after Ln, Tx = test dose signal measured after Lx. Steps 1-8 constitute one SAR cycle. The first SAR cycle measures the sensitivity corrected natural signal, and subsequent SAR cycles measure the Lx/Tx value after a series of successively increasing laboratory radiation doses (regeneration doses) administered to the sample. The regeneration doses are used to generate a dose-response curve (where ‘x’ values are the given radiation doses, and ‘y’ values are measured Lx/Tx signals) onto which the natural signal (Ln/Tn) is plotted to calculate the De value. Regeneration doses include one “zero-dose” point where no radiation dose is given, and one “repeat-dose” point (Rr), where a previous regeneration dose (R1) is given a second time.

The luminescence signals from the rock samples collected in this study were examined to determine the most appropriate SAR protocol for dating. This entailed a series of preheat plateau and dose recovery tests to determine the most appropriate preheat conditions to use, as these can vary from sample to sample. Post-IR OSL SAR protocols were tested on rock samples that showed a bright post-IR OSL signal as well as a fast component, and IRSL₅₀ SAR protocols were tested on rock samples with adequately bright IRSL₅₀ signals and no fast component (Table 4). Once a suitable IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol was established, fading measurements were conducted to determine if the IRSL₅₀ signal fading rate was adequately low that the fading correction model of Huntley and Lamothe (2001) could be applied. In samples where the fading rate was too high for correction by this model, post-IRIR₂₉₀ and MET-IRSL SAR protocols were tested. All SAR protocols tested in this study are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. SAR protocols used in this study.¹

Step	IRSL ₅₀	Post-IRIR ₂₉₀	Post-IR OSL	MET-IRSL
1	Natural/Regenerative Dose	Natural/Regenerative Dose	Natural/Regenerative Dose	Natural/Regenerative Dose
2	Preheat (180°C, 10 s)	Preheat (320°C, 10 s)	Preheat (200°C, 10 s) ²	Preheat (320°C, 60 s)
3	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s)	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s)	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x
4	Test dose (~25 Gy)	IR diodes (290°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x	Blue diodes (125°C, 40 s) → L _n , L _x	IR diodes (100°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x
5	Preheat (180°C, 10 s)	Test dose (~25 Gy)	Test dose (~25 Gy)	IR diodes (150°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x
6	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x	Preheat (320°C, 10 s)	Preheat (160°C, 10 s)	IR diodes (200°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x
7	IR diodes (200°C, 40 s)	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s)	IR diodes (50°C, 100 s)	IR diodes (250°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x
8	Return to step 1.	IR diodes (290°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x	Blue diodes (125°C, 40 s) → T _n , T _x	IR diodes (300°C, 100 s) → L _n , L _x
9		IR diodes (325°C, 40 s)	Blue diodes (220°C, 40 s)	Test dose (~25 Gy)
10		Return to step 1.	Return to step 1.	Preheat (320°C, 60 s)
11				IR diodes (50°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x
12				IR diodes (100°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x
13				IR diodes (150°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x
14				IR diodes (200°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x
15				IR diodes (250°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x
16				IR diodes (300°C, 100 s) → T _n , T _x
17				IR diodes (325°C, 100 s)
18				Return to step 1.

¹ IR diode peak emissions are centered at 870 nm wavelength and blue diode peak emissions are centered at 470 nm wavelengths. For the IRSL₅₀, post-IRIR₂₉₀ and MET-IRSL protocols, signals were detected through Schott BG-3 and BG-39 filters transmitting violet light, and for the post-IR OSL protocol, signals were detected through U-340 filters transmitting UV light.

² A 160°C preheat was applied prior to the L_x measurement for Keystone Canyon siltstone (R1) and a 200°C preheat was applied prior to the L_x measurement for Keystone Canyon siltstone (R3). See text for details.

5.1 Testing the IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol

The IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol was tested on all rock samples that did not exhibit a fast component in the quartz signal but showed a bright IRSL₅₀ from feldspar (Table 4). The SAR protocol was tested using dose recovery tests and preheat plateau dose recovery tests. A dose recovery test entails bleaching the sample (with sunlight or a light source in the reader), administering a known laboratory dose to the sample, then measuring that dose using the SAR protocol. If the SAR protocol is suitable for the sample, the ratio of the measured-to-given dose will be within 10% of unity and few aliquots or grains will be rejected from analysis due to high recuperation or recycling ratios that are not within 10% of unity.

A preheat plateau dose recovery test is similar to a dose recovery test in that the sample is bleached, then administered a known dose. In this case, however, the SAR protocol is performed using a range of preheat temperatures (steps 2 and 5 for the IRSL₅₀ protocol in Table 7). These temperatures range from 160°C to 300°C (typically with three aliquots per preheat temperature) in order to determine which preheat condition yields a measured-to-given dose ratio within 10% of unity.

5.1.1 Bowers Mansion granite

Preheat plateau dose recovery test results for Bowers Mansion granite (R3) are shown in Figure 8. Measured-to-given dose ratios (Fig. 8C) approximate 1 for preheats 160°C, 180°C and 200°C, but are greater than 1 for preheats 220-300°C. The “natural” signals, or L_n plotted as photon counts (in quotation marks because the first signal is measured from bleached and irradiated grains in this case) decrease in intensity with a preheat at 200°C and above, suggesting that a component of this signal may be thermally unstable.

When a sample yields measured-to-given dose ratios unequal to 1, this can be evidence that the preheat used in SAR is thermally transferring charge from optically insensitive traps to optically sensitive ones (e.g., Forget Brisson et al., 2020). A second experiment was run to detect thermally transferred charge (TT-OSL) that may contribute to the natural signals as a result of the preheat (plotted as hollow circles in Fig. 8C). TT-OSL is shown to be negligible relative to natural signal at preheats of 260°C and lower, but becomes a more significant component of the natural signal at higher temperatures because the natural signals are degraded.

Recycling ratio and recuperation values of the preheat plateau test results (Fig. 8D) show that, except for a few aliquots measured with preheats exceeding 240°C, nearly all aliquots are within acceptable limits (shaded areas). These preheat plateau test results suggest that SAR IRSL₅₀ protocols using preheats of 200°C or lower are suitable for the Bowers Mansion granite.

Figure 8. Preheat plateau dose recovery test results for Bowers Mansion granite (R3). One core of the sample was milled to a fine powder, and 4 mm diameter multigrain aliquot subsamples were mounted onto stainless steel discs prior to measurement. A) The IRSL₅₀ signal measured after a ~25 Gy dose was administered to the sample. B) A representative dose response curve constructed using SAR and a 10 s preheat of 180 $^{\circ}$ C and a 40 s IR hotwash at 200 $^{\circ}$ C (IRSL₅₀ protocol in Table 7). Dose units are seconds of exposure to the beta irradiation source (s). C) Measured/Given dose results for the preheat plateau test. The natural signals from 24 aliquots were depleted using a 1000 s IR stimulation at 50 $^{\circ}$ C. They were then given a laboratory dose of 25 Gy before the D_e was measured using the IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol. Preheats range from 160 $^{\circ}$ C-300 $^{\circ}$ C (3 aliquots per preheat).

5.1.2 Jessup embayment tufa

Preheat plateau dose recovery tests were conducted on both polymineral and K-feldspar (KF) fractions extracted from the tufa using the IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol. Signals measured from multi-grain aliquots of polymineral samples were slightly brighter than those measured from the KF samples, however, both responded similarly to the preheat plateau dose recovery test (Fig. 9). For both fractions, most aliquots achieved measured-to-given dose ratios within 10% of unity with the most outliers appearing at temperatures >240°C (Fig. 9B, D). Recycling ratios are generally within acceptable limits at temperatures below 240°C.

The largest difference between polymineral and KF fractions appears in their recuperation values; polymineral samples tend to have higher recuperation than the KF fractions, though recuperation does not exceed 7% in either fraction. Test results suggest that SAR IRSL₅₀ protocols with preheats of 160°C, 180°C and even 280°C may be appropriate for polymineral sediments, while protocols with preheats ranging from 160°C to 260°C may be appropriate for KF fractions. More aliquots from the polymineral fraction may be rejected from analysis due to high recuperation than the KF fraction. TT-OSL signals were not measured in these samples, however Ln signal measurements showed similar results as those from the Bowers Mansion granite, declining in intensity with increasing preheat temperature.

Tufa sample R7 yielded the largest fraction of 180-250 µm sized grains, which are most desirable for D_e measurements at the single-grain level. Thus, a dose recovery test was conducted on 500 sand grains using the IRSL₅₀ protocol in Table 7 (Fig. 10). Out of the 500 grains measured, 193 passed rejection criteria (39% acceptance rate), and the weighted mean measured-to-given dose ratio was 0.90 ± 0.01 . These results show that the sample is suitable for the IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol and that measurement of 5 single-grain discs should yield an adequate number of grains for age determination.

Figure 9. Preheat plateau dose recovery test for Jessup embayment tufa sediments. Measurements were conducted using a IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol (Table 7). A) The luminescence signal measured from a polymineral sample and a K-feldspar extract after a 1000 s IR bleach followed by a laboratory-given dose of 25 Gy. B) & C) Test results for polymineral samples. D-F) Test results for K-feldspar extracts from the same tufa. Recycling ratios (E) and recuperation values (F) are plotted separately for clarity. Measured-to-given dose and recycling ratios show acceptable results for preheats of 160-240°C for both polyminerals and K-feldspar extracts. Recuperation values for this temperature range tend to be lower for K-feldspar extracts than for polymineral samples, and signals from K-feldspar extracts are not as bright as those from polymineral samples.

Figure 10. Dose recovery test results from 180-250 μm single KF grains from Jessup embayment tufa (R7). Grains were bleached with IR diodes at 50°C for 1000 s then given a 25 Gy dose prior to measurement using the IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol in Table 7. A) A representative IRSL₅₀ signal and dose response curve from one grain is shown in 'A' and 'B', respectively. C) A kernel density estimate plot of measured-to-given dose ratios from all grains that passed rejection criteria (n=193). The weighted mean measured-to-given dose ratio is 0.90 ± 0.01 .

5.1.3 Volcanic and sedimentary rocks

Figure 11 shows dose recovery test results for volcanic and sedimentary rocks collected from Keystone Canyon and NW Coal Valley (sampling areas 1 and 7, Table 1) which exhibit a bright IRSL₅₀ signal from feldspar and no fast component from quartz (Table 4). This test was conducted using the IRSL₅₀ SAR protocol with a 180°C preheat (Table 7). One siltstone (R7) and one andesite (R2) from NW Coal Valley passed the test, but show slightly high recuperation (Fig. 11B). Future experiments on these samples should test the effect of increasing the IR stimulation duration and/or the hotwash temperature to minimize recuperated charge.

Two volcanic rocks from NW Coal Valley (R14, R5) and one siltstone from Keystone Canyon (R2) did not pass the dose recovery test (Fig. 11A), so a preheat plateau dose recovery test was conducted to determine which preheat is most appropriate for these samples (Fig. 11C, D). The test results suggest that all preheats should be adequate for the volcanic rocks and preheats ranging from 160°C to 220°C should suffice for the Keystone Canyon siltstone. These results suggest that the aliquots measured in the first dose recovery test (using a 180°C preheat) may contain anomalously behaving grains.

5.1.4 IRSL₅₀ signal fading rates

Fading rates were measured from all polymineral rock and tufa sediment samples with bright IRSL₅₀ signals from feldspar and no fast component from quartz (Table 4). Fading rates were measured using a SAR procedure outlined by Auclair et al. (2003). This procedure entails bleaching the sample, administering a known laboratory dose, preheating the sample to a temperature deemed appropriate by the preheat plateau dose recovery tests, then measuring Lx/Tx after a series of delay times ranging from a few minutes to ~10 h.

In this study I measured fading rates from several multi-grain aliquots from each sample, where the fading rate from each aliquot can be illustrated using a fading plot of Lx/Tx versus delay time (h) (Fig. 12). Delay time is plotted on a logarithmic scale to account for the fact that feldspar signals fade exponentially. The fading rate of an aliquot is quantified by the slope of the line, termed the g-value, with units of percent per decade, where a decade is a 10-fold increase in delay time (i.e., one increment on a log scale) (Huntley and Lamothe, 2001). Samples with a g-value of ~10 %/decade or higher are typically considered unsuitable for the fading correction model of Huntley and Lamothe (2001).

Fading rates measured from the Bowers Mansion granite and the Jessup embayment tufa sediments are shown in Figure 12, and representative fading rates for all other volcanic and sedimentary rock samples are shown in Figure 13. All samples exhibited low inter-aliquot variation in g-value, and an inverse relationship between g-value and g-value relative error that is due largely to limitations in photon counting statistic uncertainties represented by vertical error bars (Fig. 14). All but three samples exhibited fading rates less than 10 %/decade that can be corrected for using the model of Huntley and Lamothe (2001). Samples with overly high fading rates included the Bowers Mansion granite ($g = 12.8 \pm 0.4$ %/decade), and the NW Coal Valley rhyolite (R5) ($g = 34.4 \pm 1.1$ %/decade) and andesite (R14) ($g = 33.3 \pm 1.1$ %/decade). In the next section, the suitability of SAR protocols that target low- or negligibly-fading signals (post-IRIR₂₉₀ and MET-IRSL signals) were tested on these samples.

Figure 11. A) Dose recovery test results for 6 samples (samples 1-4 collected from NW Coal Valley, sampling area 7, Table 1, and samples 5 and 6 collected from Keystone Canyon, sampling area 1, Table 1). Three multi-grain aliquots of each sample were exposed to 1000 s of IR light to deplete their natural signal, then administered a 25 Gy laboratory dose before D_e measurement using the $IRSL_{50}$ SAR protocol (Table 7). B) Recycling ratios and recuperation values for the test shown in 'A'. Samples 3 (siltstone), 4 (andesite) and 6 (mudstone) give satisfactory measured-to-given dose ratios, with 3 and 4 having recuperation values slightly greater than 5%. All other samples show unsatisfactory measured-to-given dose ratios suggesting that the preheat conditions of the SAR protocol must be adjusted. C) Preheat plateau dose recovery test results for the samples that failed the dose recovery test in 'A'. Measurements were performed on multi-grain aliquots that were exposed to a minimum of 1000 s of IR stimulation to deplete their natural signal. A 25 Gy was administered to the samples prior to D_e measurement using the $IRSL_{50}$ SAR protocol. All three samples pass aliquot rejection criteria and yield acceptable measured-to-dose ratios for preheats 160-220°C.

Figure 12. Fading test results for 12 aliquots of Bowers Mansion granite rock sample (R3) (A, B) and polym mineral sediments from the Jessup embayment tufa (C, D). ‘A’ and ‘C’ show the cumulative g-value distribution and weighted histograms, and ‘B’ and ‘D’ show a representative fading plot. The weighted mean g-value for Bowers Mansion granite is 12.8 ± 0.4 %/decade, and that for the tufa is 7.7 ± 0.3 %/decade.

Figure 13. Representative fading plots for the samples measured in Fig. 11. Multi-grain aliquots of each sample were exposed to a minimum of 1000 s of IR stimulation to deplete their signal. A ~ 39 Gy laboratory dose was then administered to the samples and their L_x/T_x IRSL₅₀ signals were measured after a 180°C preheat and a series of delay times ranging from ~ 0.1 to ~ 10 h. A 200°C hotwash was administered after every test dose (Tx). The fading rates for two of the volcanic rocks (C, D) are too high for dating, but the fading rates of all other samples can be corrected for.

Figure 14. IRSL₅₀ g-value plotted against relative error for all measured samples.

5.2 Testing the post-IRIR₂₉₀ SAR protocol

The post-IRIR₂₉₀ SAR protocol (Table 7) was tested on Bowers Mansion granite, NW Coal Valley rhyolite (R5), and NW Coal Valley andesite (R14), all of which exhibited fading rates in excess of 10 %/decade (Figs 15 and 16). The post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal is not as bright as the IRSL₅₀ signal (compare Figs. 15A and 8A) so error resulting from photon counting statistics will be slightly higher for the post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal. As expected, the post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal yields a significant residual dose in all samples measured. All three samples yielded dose recovery test measured-to-given dose ratios in excess of 1, despite being exposed to sunlight for up to 3 h prior to the test (Figs 15C and 16A). Measured residual doses from these samples are ~33, 52 and 47 Gy for the granite, rhyolite and andesite rocks, respectively. These are slightly higher than those measured in previous studies using artificial light (solar simulators) and/or longer bleaching times (Rui et al., 2020a, and references therein), and may include a thermally transferred component (e.g., Buylaert et al., 2011) or even a phototransferred component (e.g., Neudorf et al., 2015). These residual doses will likely require correction in samples where they constitute a significant portion (i.e., 10% or more) of the palaeodose (Li et al., 2013a), but may not require correction for samples of ~500 Gy or more. Most aliquots pass recycling ratio and recuperation rejection criteria; the highest number of aliquots falling outside the shaded acceptance regions in Figs 15D and 16B come from NW Coal Valley rhyolite (R5), which lost 4 out of 8 aliquots due to poor recycling.

Figure 15. Dose recovery test results on Bowers Mansion granite (R3, 12 aliquots) using the post-IRIR₂₉₀ protocol (Table 7). Aliquots were exposed to sunlight for 2-3 h, then given a laboratory dose of 25 Gy prior to D_e measurement. A) The post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal. B) A representative dose response curve. C) Measured-to-given dose ratios above 1 indicative of a residual signal equal to 33 Gy. D) All aliquots have recuperation values within acceptable limits (<5%), and only 2 aliquots have recycling ratios that deviate from 10% of unity.

Figure 16. Dose recovery test results on two volcanic rocks from NW Coal Valley using the post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal (Table 7). Aliquots were exposed to sunlight for 2-3 h, then given a laboratory dose of 25 Gy prior to D_e measurement. A) Measured-to-given dose ratios above 1 indicative of a residual signal equal to 47 Gy for the andesite and 52 Gy for the rhyolite. D) All aliquots have recuperation values within acceptable limits (<5%), and 5 out of 16 aliquots have recycling ratios that deviate from 10% of unity.

5.2.1 Post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal fading rates

Post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal fading rates were measured from Bowers Mansion granite and the NW Coal valley rhyolite (R5) and andesite (R14), above, and were compared to their corresponding IRSL₅₀ signal fading rates (Fig. 17). Fading rates were measured using the SAR method of Auclair et al. (2003) as above, but using the post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal, preheat temperatures of 320°C and a hotwash of 325°C (Table 7). As expected, the post-IRIR₂₉₀ fading rates are lower than their corresponding IRSL₅₀ fading rates, and within the range that can be corrected for by the Huntley and Lamothe (2001) correction model. Weighted mean post-IRIR₂₉₀ g-values are 3.0 ± 0.7 , 6.9 ± 0.8 and 4.7 ± 0.6 %/decade for the granite, rhyolite and andesite, respectively.

5.3 Testing the MET-IRSL protocol

The MET-IRSL protocol is designed to target a non-fading component of the feldspar signal, eliminating the need for fading measurements and corrections (Li and Li, 2011). Such a protocol would be especially useful for samples with very high fading rates, or samples that are too old for precise correction models (>100 ka). Here, I test this protocol on the high-fading samples measured in the previous section (Bowers Mansion granite, NW Coal Valley rhyolite and andesite) as well as polymineral sediments from Jessup embayment tufa.

MET-IRSL signals from all samples are shown in Figure 18. These are somewhat similar to those reported in the literature in that the IRSL₅₀ signal is generally brighter than all signals measured at higher temperatures, and the signals are thousands of counts or less (Li and Li, 2011; Fu et al., 2012). Following Fu et al. (2012), prior to each IR stimulation, the aliquots were held at the stimulation temperature for 30 s to measure the residual isothermal thermoluminescence (ITL) after preheating ('a' and 'b' in Fig. 18A). If ITL signals are high, they may adversely affect measured IRSL signals. In these samples, ITL signals show a general increase from 50 to 300°C, with a drop at 250°C.

A dose recovery test was conducted on all four samples using the MET-IRSL protocol in Table 7 (Fig. 19). Prior to irradiation and measurement, the natural signals in all aliquots was depleted using a MET-IRSL Lx measurement (i.e., steps 2-8, Table 7). Only aliquots from the NW Coal Valley volcanic rocks passed recycling ratio and recuperation rejection criteria, and these were for stimulation temperatures of 50°C and 100°C only. No samples measured using stimulation temperatures of 200°C or higher passed rejection criteria (Fig. 19A). This prevents the detection of a non-fading signal in D_e vs stimulation temperature plots. These poor dose recovery test results may be due, in part, to i) high recuperation due to inadequate IR stimulation durations and/or, ii) ITL signals that adversely affect the IRSL signals. Fu et al. (2012) has shown that ITL effects may be reduced by holding the sample at each stimulation temperature for 100 s prior to IR stimulation, therefore future experiments will test this approach.

MET-IRSL dose response curves measured from NW Coal Valley andesite (R14) are shown in Figure 19B. Dose response curves flatten out (i.e. saturate) at lower doses with increasing stimulation temperatures, and this is consistent with observations made by Li and Li (2011) and Fu et al. (2012). In these samples, signal degradation may be occurring in response to the high preheats and stimulation temperatures in the MET-IRSL protocol (Table 7). The high preheat temperatures (320°C) required in the MET-IRSL protocol have led to a much dimmer IRSL₅₀ signal than what was observed using the IRSL₅₀ protocol (e.g., Fig. 8A), again consistent with previous observations (Fu et al., 2012).

Figure 17. Representative IRSL₅₀ and post-IRIR₂₉₀ fading plots for Bowers Mansion granite (A) and NW Coal Valley andesite (B) and rhyolite (C).

Figure 18. MET-IRSL signals for the Bowers Mansion granite (A), NW Coal Valley volcanic rocks (B, C), and K-feldspar extracted from the Jessup embayment tufa (D). The isothermal TL was measured for 30 s prior to IR stimulation at each temperature and shows a general increase in intensity from 50°C to 300°C (e.g., 'a' and 'b' in Fig. A).

Figure 19. A) MET-IRSL dose recovery test results for all four samples in Fig. 18. Prior to irradiation and measurement, the natural signals in all aliquots was depleted using a MET-IRSL measurement. Only aliquots from the NW Coal Valley volcanic rocks passed rejected criteria, and these were for stimulation temperatures of 50°C and 100°C only. No samples measured using stimulation temperatures of 200°C or higher passed rejection criteria. B) Representative MET-IRSL dose response curves for all stimulation temperatures for NW Coal Valley andesite (R14).

5.4 Testing the post-IR OSL protocol

The post-IR OSL SAR protocol was tested on siltstones R1 and R3 from Keystone Canyon. These rocks are the only samples measured that exhibit a bright OSL signal from quartz that also contains evidence of a distinct fast component (Tables 4 and 5). Preheat plateau dose recovery test results are shown in Figures 20 and 21 for samples R1 and R3, respectively. The post-IR OSL signal measured from R1 decays slowly relative to that measured from R3, and this suggests that undesirable medium and slow components may constitute a higher proportion of the signal from R1. This may explain why R1 did not respond as well to the preheat plateau dose recovery test as R3. Test results for R1 suggest that, despite few rejections due to recycling and recuperation, the only preheat suitable for this sample is 160°C as higher preheats tend to lead to over-estimates in D_e (Fig. 20D, E). D_e over-estimates in this case are likely due to thermal transfer of charge and insufficiently bleached signal arising from the medium and slow components. Test results from R3 suggest that preheats ranging from 160 to 240°C are appropriate for this sample, and aliquots are only rejected at higher temperatures due to low recycling ratios (Fig. 21D, E).

Figure 20. Preheat plateau dose recovery test results for siltstone from Keystone Canyon (R1). Measurements were made on multi-grain aliquots that were stimulated with blue diodes for 1000 s to deplete their natural signal, then given a 25 Gy laboratory dose. The D_e was then measured using the post-IR OSL SAR protocol (Table 7) using a range of preheats prior to the Lx measurement. A) & B) are the luminescence signal and dose response curve, respectively. C) & D) are recycling ratio recuperation values, respectively.

Figure 21. Preheat plateau dose recovery test results for siltstone from Keystone Canyon (R3). Measurements were made on multi-grain aliquots that were stimulated with blue diodes for 1000 s to deplete their natural signal, then given a 25 Gy laboratory dose. The D_e was then measured using the post-IR OSL SAR protocol (Table 7) using a range of preheats prior to the Lx measurement. A) & B) are the luminescence signal and dose response curve, respectively. C) & D) are the preheat plateau dose recovery test results and the recycling ratio and recuperation values, respectively.

5.5 Upper age limits of the dating technique

The upper age limit of any luminescence dating method is determined by two factors: i) the maximum radiation dose at which the dose response curve (DRC) of the sample flattens out, or saturates, and ii) the dose rate of the sediments surrounding the sample in the burial environment (D_a). A measure of the saturation level of the DRC is the “characteristic saturation dose”, also known as the D_0 value, where $D_0 = 1/e$ of the initial slope of the DRC (Bailey, 2000) (Fig. 7). The D_0 value is derived from the DRC curve model when the DRC is fitted with an exponential function of the form:

$$I = I_0 + I_{Max}(1 - e^{-D/D_0}) \quad (1)$$

where I is the luminescence signal that increases with applied dose (D), D_0 is the characteristic saturation dose, I_0 is the initial offset of the signal from zero, and I_{Max} is the upper limit to the luminescence signal intensity. Quartz OSL signals typically saturate at lower doses than feldspar, and therefore are limited to younger samples (Buylaert et al., 2007).

In a published review of quartz optical properties, Wintle and Murray (2006) suggested restricting age calculations to samples where D_e falls below $2D_0$. This rule, which effectively assigns $2D_0$ as the upper age limit of a sample, prevents large asymmetric errors in D_e that result when Ln/Tn plots on the near-flat part of the DRC. More recently, Thomsen et al. (2016) advocated for an even more conservative upper limit of D_0 based on a series of gamma ray dose recovery tests on quartz from Bordes-Fitte rockshelter in France. Although these restrictions are not appropriate for all samples (cf. Feathers et al., 2017; Neudorf et al., 2019), in this study, I provide estimates of the upper dating limit of rock and tufa samples using both the conservative and lenient approaches (Table 8).

To estimate D_0 from samples that showed dating potential in the previous sections, sample DRCs were measured using a maximum regenerative dose of ~1000 Gy and fit to an exponential function (Fig. 22). As expected, post-IR OSL signals saturate earlier than the IRSL_{50} and post- IRIR_{290} signals and the IRSL_{50} and post- IRIR_{290} show further potential for growth beyond 1000 Gy. D_0 values for the post-IR OSL signal fall just below 160 Gy providing a maximum upper age limit of 68 ka and a conservative upper age limit of ~34 ka for a dose rate of 4.7 Gy.

IRSL_{50} D_0 values average 312 Gy giving rock samples upper age limits of up to ~130 ka (conservatively ~65 ka). Post- IRIR_{290} D_0 values average 352 Gy with upper age limits of up to 165 ka (conservatively ~83 ka). Because the IRSL_{50} and post- IRIR_{290} signals measured in these samples fade (Sections 5.1.4 and 5.2.1), then fading-corrected ages beyond ~60-80 ka may only be obtained using fading correction models designed for older samples where D_e plots beyond the linear part of the DRC (e.g., Lamothe et al., 2003; Kars and Wallinga, 2009). Alternatively, further experiments may be conducted to develop a suitable MET-IRSL protocol for these samples so that fading corrections are no longer necessary (see Section 5.3).

The highest upper age limits of all samples examined were obtained from the tufa samples collected from the proposed Eetza pluvial lake shoreline deposit from Jessup embayment (Figs 2C and 3A, B). These limits are over half a million years (or ~300 ka as a conservative estimate). Such high upper age limits are possible for these samples because of the low dose rates that are characteristic of calcium carbonate-rich deposits (e.g., Jacobs et al., 2011).

Figure 22. Dose response curves for rock and tufa samples. Samples measured with the IR₅₀, post-IRIR₂₉₀ and post-IR OSL signal are shown in 'A', 'B' and 'C', respectively. Average D₀ values for each signal are plotted as a red dashed line.

Table 8. Luminescence signal characteristics for rock and tufa samples.

Sample	Target mineral	Luminescence signal ¹	Fading rate (%/decade)	Depth of light penetration (mm)	Saturation dose (D ₀) (Gy)	Dose rate (Gy/ka)	Estimated upper age limit (ka) ²	Residual dose (Gy) ³
Keystone Canyon								
Siltstone (R1)	Quartz	Post-IR OSL	N/A	2	152 ± 1	Not measured	~65 (~32)	Negligible
Siltstone (R2)	Feldspar	IR ₅₀	6.54 ± 0.49	Not sliced	306 ± 13	4.84 ± 0.26	~126 (~63)	Negligible
Siltstone (R3)	Quartz	Post-IR OSL	N/A	2.3	159 ± 2	Not measured	~68 (~34)	Negligible
Mudstone (R4)	Feldspar	IR ₅₀	4.78 ± 0.31	3.2	287 ± 9	4.38 ± 0.24	~131 (~66)	Negligible
Bowers Mansion								
Granite (R3)	Feldspar	pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.03 ± 0.70	>10	401 ± 30	4.85 ± 0.26	~165 (~83)	33
Coal Valley (Drainage Floor NW)								
Andesite (R2)	Feldspar	IR ₅₀	2.40 ± 0.53	Not sliced	241 ± 8	Not measured	~103 (~51)	Negligible
Rhyolite (R5)	Feldspar	pIRIR ₂₉₀	6.87 ± 0.75	4.4	277 ± 14	Not measured	~118 (~59)	52
Siltstone (R7)	Feldspar	IR ₅₀	3.03 ± 0.37	3	295 ± 11	Not measured	~126 (~63)	Negligible
Andesite (R14)	Feldspar	pIRIR ₂₉₀	4.74 ± 0.62	4.2	377 ± 16	Not measured	~161 (~80)	47
Jessup embayment								
Tufa polymineral sediment (R5)	Feldspar	IR ₅₀	7.74 ± 0.31	N/A	349 ± 13	1.23 ± 0.17	~576 (~284)	Negligible
Tufa K-feldspar extract (R5)	Feldspar	IR ₅₀	Not measured	N/A	394 ± 16	1.30 ± 0.17	~606 (~303)	Negligible

¹ This signal was deemed most appropriate for dating based on preheat plateau, dose recovery and fading tests. See text for explanation.

² Estimated upper ages are calculated using 2x the D₀ value following Wintle and Murray (2006), as well as the more conservative approach using D₀ following Thomsen et al. (2016) in brackets. For samples with no measured dose rate, a dose rate of 4.69 Gy was assumed, which is the average value of the measured samples from Keystone Canyon, Bowers Mansion and Coal Valley.

³ Residual signals suggest that in certain depositional environments the luminescence signal may not be completely depleted prior to deposition. In these cases, a modern sample should be measured so that the residual signal in the ancient samples can be estimated and corrected for.

5.6 Light penetration in rocks

Luminescence dating methods are not only being developed to determine the amount of time rock surfaces have been buried, but they are also being developed to determine the amount of time rock surfaces have been exposed to the sun (i.e., the exposure age) (Gliganic et al., 2019), the number of times a rock has been exposed and reburied in its lifetime (Freiesleben et al., 2015), as well as the erosion rate of rock surfaces (Brown and Moon, 2019). All of these methods are dependent on luminescence-depth profiles, which illustrate the depth of light penetration in a rock during its last (or penultimate) exposure event (Figs 23 and 24). In this study, I measured the luminescence-depth profiles of 8 rock samples that showed potential for dating to determine the depth of light penetration. These included 1 mudstone, 3 siltstones, 2 granitic rocks and 2 volcanic rocks (Fig. 25). Luminescence-depth profiles were measured from the ~1 mm slices cut from the rock cores (Section 3.2.1) using the luminescence signal shown to be most suitable for dating purposes above (Table 8).

As expected, all luminescence-depth profiles measured show a single exposure event that is the most recent exposure event in these modern surface samples (Fig. 25). Two profiles (R14 in Fig. 25C and R3 and Fig. 25D) show unexpected elevated signal intensities at 2-4 mm depth prior to decreasing to a plateau with depth into the rock. These elevated signal intensities may be due to heterogeneous mineral concentrations in the rock that have local effects on light attenuation and micro-scale dose rates (Meyer et al., 2018). Luminescence-depth profiles from the fine-grain sedimentary rocks from Coal Valley and Keystone Canyon show bleaching down to ~3 mm depth irrespective of mineral measured. Post-IRIR₂₉₀ signals measured from the volcanic rocks show bleaching down to ~4 mm depth. Post-IRIR₂₉₀ signals measured from Bowers Mansion granites show deep light penetration (≥ 10 mm) relative to their sedimentary and volcanic counterparts and similar results have been reported in past studies (Ou et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2019).

Elevated post-IRIR₂₉₀ and post-IR OSL Ln/Tn signals at the rock surfaces (depth = 0 mm) in Figure 25B, C and D are indicative of a residual signal. This suggests that ancient rock samples of similar lithologies may require correction for residual signals if the same luminescence signals are used. Future work should entail bleaching tests to determine the bleaching rates of these signals in these samples to determine whether corrections for partial bleaching are necessary in ancient rock samples.

Figure 23. Modelled (A) and measured (B) luminescence depth profiles from rocks that have experienced multiple episodes of exposure and burial (Freiesleben et al., 2015; Rades et al., 2018). A) Modelled normalized luminescence-depth profiles for multiple sequential events of burial and daylight exposure. No trap filling has been considered during daylight exposure, and the dose rate is assumed constant with depth. The sequence of events are: i) burial for a long time sufficient for saturation $L_0(x)$, ii) daylight exposure $L_1(x)$, iii) burial $L_2(x)$, iv) daylight exposure $L_3(x)$, v) burial $L_4(x)$ (Freiesleben et al., 2015). Depth has been normalized using a light attenuation factor, μ . B) A luminescence-depth profiles measured from 4 cores from a boulder obtained from a terminal moraine from Malta Valley, southern Austria. The first inset with the grey background shows the L_n/T_n for the first five slices in more detail to provide a better view on this part of the profile, which is close to the surface and therefore critical for the assessment of the bleaching front into the rock (Rades et al., 2018). The curves in the second, smaller inset (y-axis not on log scale) represent a measure of the extent of bleaching prior to burial (see Rades et al., 2018 for explanation).

Figure 24. Luminescence-depth profiles measured from coarse-grained granitic gneiss boulders from a glacial moraine in the Eastern Alps (Meyer et al., 2018). IRSL-depth profiles for the gneiss sample HT-144 (a–d) and the granitic gneiss samples HT-141 (e) and HT-145 (f). The IRSL-depth profiles in (a) were constructed based on aliquots from crushed slices (~8mm diameter) with each data point being the weighted mean of three aliquots; in (b) a block with a base area of 200×200mm was sliced and the crushed slices were density separated and feldspar extracts measured (weighted mean of five aliquots per slice and data point); in (c) intact (uncrushed) slices (~8mm diameter) were measured. Figure (d) shows all IRSL-depth profiles of sample HT-144 on a semi-log scale. The IRSL-depth profiles of sample HT-141 (e) are based on crushed slices (3 aliquots per slice and data point) and feldspar extracts (5 aliquots per slice and data point). The IRSL-depth profiles of sample HT-145 (f) are based on intact slices and crushed slices (3 aliquots per slice and data point; compare legend).

Figure 25. Luminescence-depth profiles for sliced rock samples in this study. Each data point is the weighted mean of 3 hand-ground slices. The low-intensity point in ‘B’ may record a low-dose, or opaque region in the rock caused by a heterogeneous mineral distribution (cf. Meyer et al., 2018). The low-intensity point shown in ‘C’ is a measurement artifact that resulted from sample exposure to a spark. All curves are normalized to the saturated (maximum) Ln/Tn values.

6. Discussion and Conclusions

The main goal of this pilot project was to identify suitable luminescence signals for dating rock and carbonate samples, so that future work on technique development can focus efforts on sample types and lithologies that show the most promise for dating. This research entailed testing previously published drilling, cutting and sediment extraction procedures as well as investigating the suitability of a range of luminescence signals for dating. The main conclusions of this research are discussed below.

6.1 Sample processing

Most sediment extraction procedures were successful. All cores extracted from rocks remained intact, though rock slices from coarse grained granites were more likely to crumble than those from finer grained sedimentary or volcanic rocks. Although signals from intact rock slices could not be measured in this study, past research has shown that luminescence signals from rock samples are not reduced by hand grinding (Toyoda et al., 2000; Sohbaty et al., 2011; Meyer et al., 2018), so dating rock samples should be feasible on hand ground slices, removing the need for special machine calibrations.

The smallest amount of sediment was extracted from limestone surface filings (Table 2), which limits the amount of material available for testing measurement protocols. However, this can be overcome by coring limestones and dissolving these cores to extract more sediment from below the rock surface if we can assume that the mineralogy (and therefore optical properties) of the sediment encased in the limestone is consistent throughout the rock.

Two tufa types were processed in this study: a thin, dense lithoid tufa (R5, R6) and a thicker more porous tufa (R7) (Fig. 3). Adequate amounts of sediment could be extracted from both tufas for signal testing and dating, however the porosity of some tufas such as R7 will lead to age uncertainties as young/modern sediment can penetrate tufa pores long after tufa formation. Extracting contaminating grains from tufa pores was not possible in this study. These uncertainties may be avoided by preferentially sampling dense lithoid tufas instead of porous ones, and sampling below the modern surface. If sampling porous tufas cannot be avoided, luminescence dating at the single-grain level (Fig. 10) may allow statistical analyses of D_e distributions to differentiate recently bleached contaminating grains from grains that date the depositional event of interest (Roberts et al., 2000).

6.2 Luminescence signals

Luminescence signals measured from most rock types tested in this study showed potential for dating. Preliminary signal measurements from limestones showed that 5 out of 7 samples have sufficiently bright IRSL₅₀ signals for dating, and preheat plateau and dose recovery tests showed that 10 out of 15 rocks of varying lithologies respond well to at least one of the tested SAR protocols in Table 7. Rocks with signals that are unsuitable for dating include two sedimentary rocks from the SW side of the Coal Valley basin (R1, R2), a limestone from NW Coal Valley (R11), basalt, siliceous sinter, and vein quartz.

Most rock samples respond best to dating procedures designed for feldspar. Quartz signals from few samples exhibit a fast component required for dating. Samples with high (>10 %/decade) fading rates that could not be dated using traditional IRSL₅₀ dating techniques showed dating potential using the post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal which reduced fading rates by ~77% in granite, ~80 % in rhyolite and 86% in andesite.

6.3 Upper dating limits

The upper dating limits of the quartz and feldspar signals observed in this study are similar to those reported elsewhere for sediments (e.g., Wintle and Murray, 2006; Buylaert et al., 2012, Zhang and Li, 2020). However, because upper limits presented here have been estimated from laboratory-generated DRCs, they should be interpreted with caution, as past work has shown that artificial DRCs tend to saturate at different doses than natural DRCs (Chapot et al., 2012; Timar-Gabor and Wintle, 2013; Buylaert et al., 2019).

Feldspar signals from rock samples appear to have upper age limits as high as ~160 ka, but because IRSL₅₀ and post-IRIR₂₉₀ signal DRCs continue to grow beyond 1000 Gy (Fig. 22) (and often do not flatten out until ~2000 Gy, Thiel et al., 2011), these age limits are likely conservative estimates. In tufa, upper dating limits show potential beyond half a million years as a result of its low dose rate (Table 8). This result has important implications for dating mid-Pleistocene landforms, which are beyond the upper dating limits of radiocarbon dating techniques.

6.4 Anomalous fading

A major constraint in developing suitable protocols for feldspars in rocks or tufa is the anomalous fading rate of feldspar. Fading rates can vary from sample to sample (e.g., Huntley and Lian, 2006), and even from grain to grain (e.g., Neudorf et al., 2012), therefore measurement of this rate is necessary to determine if and how corrections should be made. SAR dating techniques known to reduce or eliminate fading in feldspar have been tested here, but a datable non-fading feldspar signal could not be identified in these samples. Development of such a technique in the future should entail experiments to test more variations of the MET-IRSL protocol examined here (e.g., Rui et al., 2020b and references therein), and/or the novel post-isothermal IR technique published by Lamothe et al. (2020) earlier this year.

7. Implications and plans for future work

The purpose of this pilot project was to develop new methods in luminescence dating that are specifically calibrated to Nevada's geology and archaeology, and to expand our dating capabilities to include a broad range of sample types. Expanding our dating capabilities to rocks and carbonate deposits allows us to provide additional independent age control for features that have been dated using traditional luminescence or other methods, and has both geomorphic and archaeological implications discussed below.

7.1 Geomorphology

Geomorphically, carbonate deposits such as tufa allow us to constrain calcification events linked to wet climatic periods or pluvials. In the Great Basin, many Pleistocene and Holocene pluvial lake deposits contain significant amounts of tufa; at many sites this has been dated using radiocarbon and U-series methods (e.g., Broecker and Kaufman, 1965; Lao and Benson, 1988; Benson et al., 1990; Lin et al., 1996). Radiocarbon ages from tufa, however are susceptible to contamination by old or young carbon that can skew age results (e.g., Bischoff et al., 1993). U-series dating methods can be problematic for Holocene-aged deposits (Garnett et al., 2004) and require specific assumptions regarding the presence of detrital isotopes such as Th-230 (Lin et al., 1996, Ku and Luo, 1998). Results of this pilot project suggest that dating detrital feldspar minerals extracted from tufa using standard luminescence dating methods is possible. Such ages would not suffer from the same limitations as other dating methods, thereby providing independent age control, and would provide chronologies beyond the upper dating limit of radiocarbon dating (~55 ka). Future work will entail testing luminescence dating methods on tufa using samples with independent age constraints and developing effective ways to measure and model environmental dose rates for these samples. Preliminary dose rate calculations made in this study suggest that tufa luminescence ages may be

obtained from deposits that are up to 500 ka in age or older. Therefore, future work will also entail investigating the feasibility of dating mid-Pleistocene landforms in the Great Basin, such as pluvial lake shorelines that have yet to be dated using absolute dating methods (Reheis et al., 2002; 2014).

Rock surface dating can help us determine the earliest time of formation of many landforms because pebbles, cobbles or boulders comprising their heaviest and most stable constituents are less prone to post-depositional re-working than sand (e.g., Simms et al., 2011). Rock surface ages, in combination with ages from sediments can also help us visualize transport histories of a broad range of grain sizes in coastal, lacustrine, fluvial, or glacial systems (e.g., Rades et al., 2018; Chiverrell et al., 2020). Future work will entail developing effective ways to measure environmental dose rates for rock surfaces in various depositional contexts by testing rock surface dating techniques using independently dated landforms. Rock surface dating techniques will then be applied to cobbles and pebbles forming gravelly pluvial lake shoreline features in the Great Basin, where previously dated sands and silts sampled from gravel matrices have led to age underestimates.

Luminescence-depth profiles of rocks not only provide information on the depth of light penetration during exposure events but also provide information on the transport history of the rocks (Fig. 23). Luminescence-depth profiles, in conjunction with surface exposure luminescence ages from bedrock have even enabled high-resolution reconstructions of post-Little Ice Age glacier fluctuations (Lehmann et al., 2018). Future research will develop luminescence surface exposure dating techniques using age comparisons with cosmogenic ages (in collaboration with Dr. Bad Sion, DRI) and other independent age controls. It is anticipated that by dating glacial deposits such as moraines, erratics, and other glacial debris we can constrain the time of past ice retreat during warming periods. Future research will also investigate to what extent luminescence-depth profiles can differentiate between various modes of sediment transport on Earth's surface. For example, can rock luminescence-depth profiles differentiate between supraglacial (or proglacial) sediments and subglacial (or englacial) sediments in ancient glacial deposits that, due to their massive and chaotic structure, are otherwise enigmatic in terms of their origin (Dreimanis, 1989)? Such questions can help us understand the behavior of ancient ice sheets and glaciers and their response to climate.

7.2 Archaeology

Archaeological implications of rock surface dating include better age constraints for monuments, buildings or walls using burial age dating techniques (e.g., Sohbaty et al., 2015; Feathers et al., 2019; Khasawneh et al., 2019; Liritzis et al., 2019). These studies often combine luminescence ages from sediments and rocks to validate previous age estimates and to unravel the complexities of site formation over time. Luminescence-depth profiles have provided evidence of long-term use and reuse of monuments and infrastructure (e.g., Sohbaty et al., 2015) and show potential for identifying multiple phases of building and re-building by humans in the past. Surface exposure luminescence dating techniques also show potential for providing age constraints for lithic quarry sites using flake scars in bedrock (Gliganic et al., 2019).

In the short-term, results of this pilot project will inform future work that aims to develop and refine luminescence dating methods for artifacts and archaeologically significant landforms and sediments in Coal Valley, Lincoln County, NV (in collaboration with Dr. Teresa Wriston, DRI). This research intends to use novel luminescence dating methods to determine how people responded to changing environmental conditions in the late Pleistocene and Holocene in Lincoln County. Luminescence ages from the rocks (or rock artifacts) and sediments will help answer archaeological questions, target archaeological survey areas, evaluate archaeological site integrity, and refine chronological control so that cultural changes can be revealed.

In the longer term, results of this pilot project will inform future proposals that aim to answer questions regarding early human migration, settlement and subsistence patterns in the Great Basin and elsewhere, as well as when and how North America's very first human settlers arrived (e.g., Darvill et al., 2018; Davis et al., 2019). In

Canada, for example, rock surface dating methods have the potential to provide age constraints on the construction and use of Indigenous clam gardens constructed in the intertidal zone of the Pacific Northwest coast (Neudorf et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2019). Such age constraints would be immune to marine reservoir effects that are a source of uncertainty in radiocarbon dates and would be less likely to yield age underestimates due to sediment re-working. Future work will also investigate the potential of rock surface dating in assessing the integrity of archaeological sites; such work often entails differentiating between natural earth surface processes and anthropogenic disturbance (e.g., Neudorf, 2016; Neudorf and Lian, 2017). Constraining the time of placement of rocks or rock artifacts at a site can confirm or negate hypotheses about past human behavior.

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